

**PSYCHOLOGY OF PRESCHOOL CHILDREN AND ITS STATUS OF
LEARNING.**

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Аннотация: В этой статье описывается использование потенциала проективной методики в изучении семейных отношений дошкольных детей

Ключевые слова: дошкольное возраст, семейные отношения, «я», рисунок семьи, отношение к родителям, психологический портрет,

Annotation: This article describes the use of the potential of the projective technique in the study of family relations of preschool children

Keywords: Preschool age, family relationships, "I", family drawing, attitude to parents, psychological portrait

In Uzbekistan, positive work on strengthening families, their social protection, raising a well-rounded person, spiritually mature, physically healthy generation is being expressed. In this regard, in accordance with the decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On additional measures to increase the effectiveness of spiritual and educational work" dated May 3, 2019 No. PQ-4307, guaranteed preparation of young people for independent life, To develop and implement a methodology based on gradualism and continuity of education, starting from the period of pregnancy and continuing until the age of 18, to direct young people to self-development as individuals, to educate them as active citizens with a wide outlook, "Continuous spiritual concept of education" was approved. Compared to social education, family education has a profound effect on children's mental world, emotions and feelings. In the current conditions, spiritual and moral relations based on universal and national values, reflecting oriental moral characteristics are being established in families, and legal, moral and spiritual foundations are being improved in families. If a healthy moral environment, a culture of mutual interaction, and a moral principle do not take deep root at home, it is inevitable that there will be a void and negative situations in the family. Many people think about the question of when to start raising a child. Many scholars have given different answers to it. In particular, Ibn Sina noted that it is necessary to deal with the upbringing of a child before its birth, from the womb, and education up to the age of five is very important in the formation of a child's personality. It is in the preschool period that universal human qualities are formed that help the child to be successful in all future activities and in life in general. All this develops in various activities through the personal activity of the child, the support of adults in a positive environment in the family.

The main task of the preschool education organization is to create a positive psychological microclimate and conditions in the organization in order to ensure the maximum development of each child's personality and his preparation for the next stage of development. What is required from parents and educators is a lot of patience, love and a scientifically based approach to child rearing. As a result of proper education, the child is ready to think

independently and take a bold step into a big life[10]. It is very important for preschool children to understand their "I" in the family. Educators and psychologists have studied the problems of the family, its traditions and traditions, the influence of the family on the formation of the child's personality in many studies. A child is not only a product of parental influence. He understands and accepts his family in his own way. Defines his place in the family in interaction and realizes himself as a person in the family. Children evaluate family events differently than adults. Only when we get used to seeing the world around us through the eyes of a child, can we properly understand them, help them with their excitement and sorrow. In today's applied psychology and child psychology, the perception of the child as an individual in the family of preschool children and its impact on the general mental development of the child, the formation of ideas about social roles within the framework of the interaction of family members, the composition of communication skills and competencies through imitation of adults such issues are being studied.

DISCUSSION AND RESULTS

Currently, there are many psychodiagnostic tools, tests, methods, questionnaires and they are widely used. One such diagnostic tool is the popular projective test called "Family Picture". The famous "Family Picture" test, developed by the Estonian psychologist G. Homentaukas, is a tool that helps adults see the world through the eyes of a child. This test provides an understanding of the child's personal assessment of his family, his relationships with family members, what the child cannot perceive, what he feels with strong emotion. What worries the child subconsciously, the same things are expressed in children's drawings. A family picture is a psychological portrait of a child's personality. This test can be used in children between 3 and 10 years of age. Psychologists use this test to study the "I" of the child in the family. This test is convenient and popular in pedagogical and psychological practice. This test can be conducted by teachers, psychologists of educational institutions and even parents.

To conduct the research, you need a white paper 21 x 29 cm in size, an eraser. The child is told: "Please draw a picture of your family." But what "family" is is not explained, because the test requirement requires it. There is no time limit when the task of drawing is given. When the child completes the task, you should pay attention to the following: the sequence of drawing the contents, deletion of the contents, giving the child comments, emotions, etc.

After completing the task, the child will be asked the following questions and interviewed:

- 1) Tell me, who did you draw in this picture?
- 2) Where are they?
- 3) What are they doing?
- 4) Are they happy or bored with something?
- 5) Which of them is happy? Why?

6) Which of them is very unhappy? Why?

When analyzing the results of the "Family Picture" methodology, it is desirable to know the age of the child, the number of family members, and the age of the brothers, sisters, or sisters.

Also, when analyzing a picture drawn by a child, it is necessary to pay attention to the information in the conversation and the following scales:

1) The child's real family is compared with the family picture he draws. If the relationships and atmosphere in the family are positive, the child will draw a picture of all members of the family. If one of the family members is not drawn in the picture, then the family situation is not perfect.

2) If the picture depicts people who are not related to the family: a) neglect, isolation, b) strong level of anxiety.

3) usually, children forget to draw with which member of the family there is a conflict problem. In most cases, brothers or sisters do not draw pictures of siblings. With this, the child expresses his superiority in the family, his lack of love for his father and mother. For example, a child drew himself between his father and mother, but did not draw his younger brother or sister at all.

4) If the child does not draw his picture or draws only himself instead of his family, then this indicates a lack of unity in the family.

5) If, instead of his family, the child draws animals and birds, then the child lacks attention and emotional tenderness.

6) If the child drew a picture of family members holding hands and in a row, then the psychological climate in this family is good. If not, it means the opposite.

7) If the family members are drawn in groups, it means that there are small groups in the family

8) The presence of many compositions and colors in the clothes of family members indicates positive family relations, and on the contrary, if there is enmity in family relations, the bodies of family members are drawn incompletely, without clothes or unfinished [8].

9) Children usually draw their father and mother very big. So, family relationships are based on equality, the child feels like an adult in the family.

10) If children draw themselves bigger than their father and mother, then the level of self-esteem of the child is very high.

THE MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY

VOLUME-3, ISSUE-4

11) If the child feels very small compared to other family members, he/she needs to be cared for by his/her parents.

12) If the child drew his picture with his hands up and his fingers extended, this indicates his aggressiveness. Sometimes such pictures show that the children are aggressive towards the people around them, but this condition is hidden and the child is strong and wants to dominate others.

13) If a child draws the hands of family members with fists formed and fingers in a long position, then he feels that this family member is aggressive towards him.

14) If the child has drawn his teeth big, then he has a strong tendency to bite, shout, and be rude. If the child draws other family members in such a position, he will feel fear and hostility towards this family member.

The family picture test is related to the child's age characteristics. Children aged 3-4 draw the human body incompletely with lines. The pictures of 5-7-year-old children are much richer, the body structures are complete, and the pictures are completed. Therefore, family pictures drawn by children should be carefully analyzed paying attention to every detail. A quantitative assessment system was developed for this test and 5 different symptom complexes were distinguished. 52 5-7-year-old children attending MTT participated in our study. It is known that the method of kinetic painting of the family does not only reflect the present and the past, but also focuses on the future, because the child tries to understand the situation while drawing, family relationships are resolved.

Kinetic painting of the family consists of two parts: painting and talking after the painting. During the study, children were given white paper, a black pen and an eraser according to the instructions. After the task was explained, the children drew with great interest. Children were divided into 2 groups, 1st group was 5-6 years old, 2nd group was 6-7 years old. During the drawing with the children, they commented on the pictures they were drawing, including, mom is standing here, my sister is not visible because she is asleep, can I draw my mom twice because my dad is not there?, can I draw my grandfather? such comments were observed. The children showed the pictures they drew to each other and explained them. Based on the results of the interview with the children who completed the drawing, the analysis was generally reflected as follows.

CONCLUSION

The method of kinetic painting of the family does not only reflect the present and the past, but also focuses on the future, because the child tries to understand the situation when drawing, interprets the interpersonal relationships in the family expressed in his picture in his own way, and shows his vision of the family. In each picture, the social roles of "parents" in the imagination of the child are reflected, the psychology of family relations is visible. According to the results of the experiment, 71.4% of the test subjects drew their father and mother too big, so it can be concluded that the relationship in the family is based on equality, and the child feels like an adult in the family. The presence of an environment that has a positive effect on the

formation of the child's personality in such families is certainly gratifying. However, 19% of children drew animals and birds instead of their families, it is a pity that such children lack attention and emotional tenderness in their families. A child growing up in such an environment has low self-confidence, shyness, difficulty in communicating, inability to think independently.

According to researchers, the relationship between parents and children is the leading factor in the formation of a child's personality. Studying the perceptions of preschool children about the family, information about the family environment of each child and the attitude of the parents to the child serve as an important resource for educators-pedagogues in cooperation with the family. This ensures the quality and efficiency of the educational process carried out in preschool educational institutions.

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